

The starting material, 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1-tetralone (II) was prepared in 50% yield by alkylating 7-methoxy-1-tetralone with *p*-methoxybenzyl chloride in presence of sodamide. The tetralone (II) was then reduced by the Clemmensen method (Martin's modification) for fifty hours when 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III) was obtained as a highly viscous substance in 62% yield, which was reduced with lithium and ethyl alcohol in liquid ammonia (Wilds and Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5366), and the resulting tetrahydro derivative was hydrolysed and isomerised with 10% sulphuric acid (cf. Bentley and Firth, *loc. cit.*) to obtain 7-(4'-keto-cyclohex-2'-enylmethyl)-1:9-octalone-2 (IV) in 69% yield. This was characterised by its deep red *bis*-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and its UV-absorption spectrum.

Again, 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1-tetralone (II) was allowed to react with excess of ethylmagnesium bromide, when it furnished on distillation with a trace of iodine 1-ethyl-7-methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (VI) in 72% yield. The intermediate tertiary carbinol could not be isolated due to spontaneous dehydration during its distillation. The question as to whether the double bond in the endo position as in (VI) or the exo position or both, has not been ascertained as it is of no consequence in the present work so long as the double bond remains conjugated with the benzene ring. However, the compound (VI) could be obtained in a crystalline form, and was subjected to lithium-liquid ammonia-alcohol reduction. The resulting hydro-derivative was then hydrolysed and isomerised with 10% sulphuric acid to obtain 7-(4'-keto-cyclohex-2'-enylmethyl)-8-ethyl-1:9-octalone-2 (VII), which was characterised through its deep red *bis*-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and by its UV-absorption spectrum. The values of the absorption maxima and extinction coefficients in the case of (IV) and (VII) are very close to those reported by Bentley and Firth (*loc. cit.*) for similar structures.

The biological assay of these compounds is on hand.

* EXPERIMENTAL

7-Methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1-tetralone (II).—To a fine suspension of freshly prepared sodamide in dry benzene (100 c.c.) was added dropwise with efficient stirring

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strass, Oxford.

a solution of 7-methoxy-1-tetralone (8.8 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed on the steam-bath for 15 hours, when the sodium salt of the tetralone separated. To this was then added a solution of *p*-methoxybenzyl chloride (7.8 g.) in dry ether (25 c.c.). After standing for half an hour the mixture was refluxed on the steam-bath for 8 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was then poured on iced HCl. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with benzene. The combined extract was washed free of acid, dried (Na_2SO_4) and stripped off the solvents. The residual mass on distillation under reduced pressure yielded 7.4 g. (50%) of the benzylated product (II) as a stiff substance, b.p. $247\text{--}50^\circ/6$ mm. On keeping it solidified, Crystallisation from methanol afforded beautiful shining flakes, m.p. 89° . (Found: C, 76.6; H, 6.82. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.00; H, 6.80 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (II) was prepared by the usual procedure (H_2SO_4 method) except that the reaction mixture had to be heated on the water-bath for half-an-hour when the hydrazone derivative formed slowly as dark red crystals; it was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture as deep red needles, m.p. $200\text{--}201^\circ$. (Found: N, 11.40. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 11.76 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III).—The above ketone (5.56 g.) was reduced by the Clemmensen method (Martin's modification) with amalgamated zinc wool (10 g.), HCl (conc., 13 c.c.), water (6 c.c.) and toluene (25 c.c.). A negative response in coloration with a drop of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine chloride solution was obtained after 48 hours of refluxing during which period HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) was added every six hours. The organic layer was then taken up completely in ether, the ether-toluene layer washed with water and then stripped off the solvents. The residue, which gave a coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, thus indicating demethylation, was methylated by refluxing with dimethyl sulphate (5 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.) and potassium carbonate (2.7 g.). After 3 hours, acetone was removed and the carbonate dissolved by addition of iced water. The organic product was taken up in ether and after the usual working up, the residue yielded 3.5 g. (62%) of 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (III) as a viscous mass, b.p. $225^\circ\text{--}230^\circ/4$ mm. (Found: C, 80.70; H, 7.68. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 80.81; H, 7.85 per cent).

7-(4'-Ketocyclohex-2'-enylmethyl)-1:9-octalone-2 (IV).—Reduction of (III) (2.82 g.) was accomplished by dissolving it in ether (100 c.c.) and liquid ammonia (150 c.c.) and adding lithium (1.26 g.) and ethyl alcohol (11.1 g.) following exactly the procedure described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) for the reduction of 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-anisyl)-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene. The reaction mixture was similarly worked up and the product was hydrolysed by heating with 10% H_2SO_4 on the steam-bath for 5 hours. The organic layer was then taken up in ether and the ethereal layer washed free of acid and then dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure and it furnished 1.1 g. (55%) of the diketone (IV) as a viscous colorless oil, b.p. $220^\circ\text{--}225^\circ/5$ mm., $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$, 220 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ 9,972). (Found: C, 79.10; H, 8.60. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 79.03; H, 8.58 per cent).

The bis-2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture as deep red needles, m.p. 120-21° (sintering at 102°). (Found : N, 18.44. $C_{22}H_{20}O_8N_8$ requires N, 18.12 per cent).

7-Methoxy-1-ethyl-2-(*p*-1-ethoxybenzyl)-3 : 4-dihydronaphthalene (VI).—To a cooled solution of ethylmagnesium bromide (from 4.4 g. ethyl bromide, 0.96 g. Mg and 20 c.c. anhydrous ether) was added dropwise a solution of 7-methoxy-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-1-tetralone (II, 5.9 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (30 c.c.). After 2 hours the mixture was refluxed on the steam-bath for 6 hours and then decomposed with iced HCl. The hydrolysate was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was freed of acid and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was aspirated and the residual oil distilled under reduced pressure in presence of a trace of iodine, when 4.4 g. (72%) of 7-methoxy-1-ethyl-2-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-3 : 4-dihydronaphthalene (VI) was obtained, b.p. 230°-235°/5 mm., which solidified on keeping, and on crystallisation twice from methyl alcohol it melted at 102°. (Found : C, 80.86 ; H, 7.84. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 81.04 ; H, 8.16 per cent).

7-(4'-Ketocyclohex-2'-enylmethyl)-8-ethyl-1 : 9-octalone-2 (VII).—A solution of (VI, 3.08 g.) in anhydrous ether (100 c.c.) and liquid ammonia (200 c.c.) was reduced with lithium (1.26 g.) and ethyl alcohol (11.1 g.), following exactly the procedure described for the reduction of 1-ethyl-2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-7-methoxy-3 : 4-dihydronaphthalene (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 714). Hydrolysis and migration of the double bonds to $\alpha\beta$ -positions were effected by treatment with 10% H_2SO_4 on the steam-bath for 5 hours. The hydrolysate was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer washed free of acid and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent the residue gave 1.8 g. (62%) of 7-(4'-ketocyclohex-2'-enylmethyl)-8-ethyl-1 : 9-octalone-2 (VII) as a colorless viscous oil, b.p. 225-28°/5 mm., λ_{max}^{nic} , 222 μ (ϵ 10,021). (Found : C, 80.05 ; H, 8.80. $C_{19}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 79.70 ; H, 9.09 per cent).

The bis-2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the above ketone was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture in deep orange plates, m.p. 135° (sintering at 120°). (Found : N, 17.70. $C_{31}H_{34}O_8N_8$ requires N, 17.34 per cent).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
HOSEIARPUR.

Received May 10, 1956.